

Study of Appendicitis in Children: Retrospective Study**Sandeep.Hambarde¹, Thavendraj.Dihare², Uttaml.Wadavkar³, Ashwini S. Hambarde⁴**¹AssociateProfessor, Department of General Surgery, LNCT Medical College and Sewakunj Hospital, Indore – 451010 Madhya Pradesh²AssociateProfessor, Department of Pediatric Surgery, Govt. Medical College, Nagpur – 440001 Maharashtra³Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, DVVPFMCH, Vilatghat, Ahmednagar – 414001 Maharashtra⁴AssociateProfessor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, School of Medical Sciences, Sehore, Madhya Pradesh

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Abstract:**Background:** Appendicitis is a lymphatic organ; it is much longer in children than adults because other lymphatic organs are not well developed to combat infection. Hence, appendix is more commonly infected in children. It leads to a surgical emergency.**Materials and Methods:** 90 children with appendicitis aged between 4-10 years. A total of 90 children were studied, with 45 being male and 45 being female. Appendicitis symptoms were noted and confirmed with a USG/ST scan, were operated on by general anesthesia and the dissected part was sent to histopathology examination to rule out the exact pathology.**Result:** The highest prevalence of acute appendicitis was observed in both sexes. 26 (57.7%) in males, 23 (51%) in female children. The least number of perforations was observed in both sexes i.e. 12 (26.6%) in males and 6 (13.3%) in females.**Conclusion:** The present study will help the surgeons classify the types of appendicitis and treat the surgical emergency of appendicitis in children efficiently to avoid morbidity and mortality in children.

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Introduction

Acute appendicitis is a common surgical emergency among children below 10 years of age. The majority of children presenting with abdominal pain have acute appendicitis. Despite the availability of advanced diagnostic imaging, the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in young children remains a challenge for surgeons because the late approach to medical aid leads to the perforation of appendicitis with abscess formation and generalized peritonitis with sepsis. Overlap of symptoms with many other common childhood illnesses, together with the inability of children to express themselves, and difficult abdominal examinations in children. Hence, an attempt was made to evaluate the types of appendicitis and the symptoms of appendicitis.

Materials and Methods

90 (ninety) children regularly visited the surgery department of LNCT Medical College, Indore with Govt. Medical College, Nagpur and DVVPFMCH, Vilatghat, Ahmednagar were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: Children of both sexes below ten years of age with symptoms of appendicitis confirmed by USG and/or CT scan were selected for study.**Exclusion Criteria:** Children diagnosed with Meckel's diverticulum, volvulus and malignancy in the right iliac fossa that had any congenital anomalies were excluded from the study.**Method:**

Every patient presented abdominal pain with Macburney's tenderness; appendicitis was confirmed by USG/CT scan. A routine blood examination was carried out to rule out any other clinical manifestations and excised appendix was sent to histopathological examination.

The duration of the study was from September 2012 to September 2015.

Statistical Analysis: Types of appendicitis in both sexes were classified by percentage. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software. The ratio of male and female children was 1:1.

Results

Perforated appendicitis: (a) 9(20%) were aged between 5-6 years; (b) 3(6.6%) were aged between 9-10 years. Acute appendicitis: 13 (28.8%) in the age group of 5-6 years, 8 (17.7%) in the age group of 7-8 years, and 5 (11.1%) in the age group of 9-10 years of age.

Chronic appendicitis: 2(4.4%) in the group of 5-6 years, 2(4.4%) in the age group of 7-8 years, and 3 (6.66%) in the age group of 9-10 years. Perforated appendicitis: 4(8.8%) years of age, 2(4.4%) in the group of 9-10 years.

Figure 1: Prevalence of appendicitis in Male children (aged between 5 to 10 years)

Figure 2: Prevalence of appendicitis in Female children

Table 1: Prevalence of Appendicitis in male Children (aged between 5 to 10 years)

Sr. No.	Types of Appendicitis	Age group	No. of Patient	Percentage (%)
1	Perforated Appendicitis	a) 5-6 Yrs	9	20
		b) 9-10 Yrs	3	6.66
2	Acute Appendicitis	a) 5-6 Yrs	13	28.8
		b) 7-8 Yrs	8	17.7
		c) 9-10 Yrs	5	11.1
3	Chronic Appendicitis	a) 5-6 Yrs	2	4.44
		b) 7-8 Yrs	2	4.44
		c) 9-10 Yrs	3	6.66

Table 2: Prevalence of Appendicitis in Female Children (aged between 5 to 10 years)

Sr. No.	Types of Appendicitis	Age group	No. of Patient	Percentage (%)
1	Perforated Appendicitis	a) 5-6 Yrs	4	8.8
		b) 9-10 Yrs	2	4.4
2	Acute Appendicitis	a) 5-6 Yrs	8	17.7
		b) 7-8 Yrs	13	28.8
		c) 9-10 Yrs	2	4.4
3	Chronic Appendicitis	a) 5-6 Yrs	6	13.3
		b) 7-8 Yrs	6	13.3
		c) 9-10 Yrs	4	8.8

Acute appendicitis: 8 (17.7%) in the age group of 5- 6 years, 13 (28.8%) in the age group of the age group of 7-8 years, and 2 (4.4%) in the age group of 9-10 years. Chronic appendicitis: 6 (13.3%) in the age group of 5-6 years, 6 (13.3%) in the age group in the age group of 7-8 years, and 4 (8.8%) in the age group of 9-10 years.

Discussion

Present study of the prevalence of appendicitis in children in Maharashtra. In male children, perforated appendicitis was found in 9 (20%) of the age group of 5-6 years and in 3 (6.66%) of the age group of 9-10 years. Acute appendicitis was observed in 13 (28.8%) in 5-6 years of age, 8 (17.7%) in 7-8 years of age, and 5 (11.1%) in 9-10 years of age. Chronic appendicitis was observed in 2 (4.4%) in the age group of 5-6 years, 2 (4.4%) in the age group of 7-8 years, and 3 (6.6%) in the age group of 9-10 years [Table 1]. In female children, perforated appendicitis was 4 (8.8%) in the 5-6 years and 2 (4.4%) in the 9-10 years. Acute appendicitis was observed in 8 (17.7%) in 5-6 years of age, 13(28.6%) in 7-8years, and 2 (4.4%) in 9-10 years of age. Chronic appendicitis was observed in 6 (13.3%) in 5-6 years of age, 6 (13.3%) in 7-8 years of age, and 4 (8.8%) in 9-10 years of age [Table 2]. These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies. [5- 7]

The percentage of perforated appendicitis in male children was 25%, while in female children it was just 10%, and in acute appendicitis, it was 57% in male children while in female children it was 50%. It clearly indicates that the severity and medical emergency of appendicitis are greater in male children than female children. [8] In children of both sexes aged between 5-6 years, having perforated

appendicitis can cause serious complications such as peritonitis and abscess formation, which increases morbidity and long stays at the hospital and hospital costs too. Because of delay in diagnosis and misinterpretation of history and physical examination, radiological study becomes the ultimate diagnostic factor for appendicitis in children. [10]

Abdominal pain is the most common presenting symptom, followed by vomiting, fever, and anorexia. On examination, localized tenderness in the right lower quadrant predominates over diffuse tenderness. Other physical signs include involuntary guarding, rebound tenderness, and a temperature greater than 37°C. An increased WBC count and an elevated neutrophil count are two of the laboratory diagnoses, but C-reactive protein (CRP) is non-specific. It has sensitivity ranging from 43% to 92% only in children with appendicitis, [12] Hence, ultimately, radiological (USG/CT scan) factors are decisive or confirmatory.

Conclusion

The present study of the prevalence of appendicitis in children below ten years had more incidence of acute appendicitis and the least incidence of perforated appendicitis. It needs a proper physical examination, a complete blood examination (CBC count) and ultimately a radiological examination to confirm appendicitis in children. A delayed approach to medical aid will cause a higher rate of morbidity and mortality.

Limitations: Owing to the tertiary location of the research center. The small number of patients, and the lack of the latest techniques, we have limited findings and results.

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